

Setup TWOSEX-MSChart program

設定兩性生命表程式

Age-stage, two-sex life table: the prime tool of ecology, biocontrol, pest management, and sustainable development

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140.120.197.173/Ecology

Laboratory of Theoretical Ecology
理論生態學研究室 Hsin Chi

Science, Theory, Simulation Models, Statistics

Introduction

Italiano Français Español 中文 Portuguese Deutsch РУССК

Ecology Software
生態學軟件

Publication
論文

Photo Gallery
攝影藝廊

Left photo: A man in a white jacket standing in front of a stone archway in a snowy landscape.

Right photo: A man in a white jacket sitting with two women in front of a stone wall.

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Ecological Software

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Ecology Software by Hsin Chi

The following software are designed in Visual BASIC 6 (Service Pack 4). They are also available for non-profit or academic use and can be downloaded from <http://nhsbig.inhs.uiuc.edu/wes/chi.html> (Illinois Natural History Surveys, USA).

Educational Software (Click here)

Exponential growth, logistic growth, competition, predation, distribution analysis,etc.

Note well: Ecology is a young science. All these programs are only for basic education, because they are based on over-simplified models (not theories). You should not use them in your research.

請注意：

生態學是一門很年輕的科學。因為這些教學用模式都是過於簡化的，本網頁頁所有程式僅能用於教學，不宜用於研究。

Advanced Software (Click here)

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進階生態學程式

對多數科學家而言，生命表理論相當困難。生命表資料是真正的「大數據」，包含整個種群的存活率、發育率、繁殖率、性比率、齡期變化等等，而這些因子都隨年齡與齡期而改變。分析這些資料時，不可以將各項目分開單獨分析。例如：只分析發育速率（例如不同溫度下的發育速率）時，則忽略了存活率與繁殖率，所得到的結果會以偏概全。唯有利用生命表理論，才能同時考慮所有因子。因為大數據的分析十分困難，為協助學者分析生命表資料，本人提供TWOSEX軟件免費供學者使用，僅要求學者遵守學術道德與誠實引用。

生命表只是種群生態學研究的起點，唯有將生命表與捕食率結合，才能進一步研究生物防治與害蟲治理，也才能合理規劃大量飼育天敵、預測施藥時期與次數、釋放天敵時機與次數。建議使用者進一步學習CONSUME（可用於取食量、捕食率、寄生率的分析），再與TIMING（預測害蟲種群生長）結合，就能做好害蟲治理與生物防治。

為協助各校師生學習生命表理論、捕食理論、電腦模擬、資料分析、科學繪圖、論文寫作，本人提供完整的課程（至少三天），有需要之學校與單位可與本人聯繫 (hsinchi@dragon.nchu.edu.tw)。（[課程綱要](#)）

Download TWOSEX-MSChart

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New Tab Prof. Dr. Hsin Chi (...) 網路郵局 第一銀行First Bank... Laboratory of Theor... Reading list

直接執行版 EXE version

1. [TWOSEX-MSChart-exe-B100000.rar \(Version 2021.12.05\)](#)
2. [TIMING-MSChart-exe.rar \(Version 2021.11.20\)](#)
3. [CONSUME-MSChart-exe.rar \(Version 2021.11.20\)](#)
4. [Probit-MSChart-exe.rar \(Version 2021.11.15\)](#)
5. [LeafArea-exe.rar](#)

安裝版 Setup version

若無法使用 "exe" 版本，則必須使用下列版本安裝。解壓縮後至於桌面。最好安裝於C碟。若安裝後仍有問題，可以進入Support資料匣中直接以管理員身分執行程式檔。

If you cannot run the "exe" version, you have to setup the following versions. They are now in English interface. It will be easier for you. It is better to setup the program in C: drive. If you still face difficulty after setup, you can go into the Support folder and run the EXE file as administrator.

1. [TWOSEX-MSChart-B100000.rar \(Version 2021.12.05\)](#)
2. [TIMING-MSChart.rar \(Version 2021.11.20\)](#)
3. [CONSUME-MSChart.rar \(Version 2021.11.20\)](#)
4. [Probit-MSChart.rar \(Version 2021.11.15\)](#)
5. [LeafArea.rar](#)

Because CONSUME and TIMING are linked to TWOSEX, if you include predation rate in the simulation of population growth and predation potential, you have to make sure all three programs are the most up-to-date ones.

TWOSEX-MSChart has been used on Windows and Mac system

- TWOSEX has been used on Windows XP, 7, 8, 10, 11. In most cases, there will be no problem.
- If you use Chinese or non-ASCII codes for the folder names, you may encounter some problems. But you can always find a solution for that. Only in extreme cases, you may have to re-install your operating system.
- On Mac computer, you have to use Windows operating system to run TWOSEX.

Four ways to run TWOSEX

1. Extract TWOSEX-MSChart-exe-B100000.rar, run TWOSEX-MSChart.exe (or similar) as administrator.
2. Extract TWOSEX-MSChart-B100000.rar, run **setup.exe**. Then run TWOSEX as a Windows program.
3. Extract TWOSEX-MSChart-B100000.rar and put it on Desktop, run the program directly from the **Support folder**. (Run as administrator).
4. In rare cases, you have to install OCX (active control).

1. Run TWOSEX-MSChart.exe

- Download TWOSEX-MSChart-exe-100000.rar
- Extract it and save Twosex-MSChart...exe to Desktop.

- Run as administrator.

2. Setup TWOSEX

2.1. Download TWOSEX-MSChart-B100000.rar and extract it to the desktop.

2.2. Run Setup.exe

2.3. Click on “OK”

2.4. Click this button to install

2.5. Click on Continue

2.6. If you see this, just click Yes.

2.7. Setup was successfully

2.8. Run TWOSEX

3. Run TWOSEX-MSChart.exe from the Support folder.

If you see these error messages or other similar messages, you can extract the RAR file and put it on the **Desktop**. Then you can run the program from the **Support** folder.

Run-time error '52'

Run-time error '339'

3.1. Go to the folder Support

3.1.

3.2. Run Twosex-MSChart-2020... as administrator

If you cannot setup at all,

- If you are using Windows XP, you may face trouble and will not be able to setup the program.
- Extract TWOSEX-MSChart.rar to a new folder on your Desktop.
- Open the **Support folder**, find the file **TWOSEX-MSChart.exe**.
- Use right mouse key to click on it.
- Select “Run as administrator”.

4. Register OCX component to your computer (特殊狀況)

If you cannot run TWOSEX-MSChart.exe and you see this message (or similar), then you have to install the OCX file in order to run the program.

How to register an OCX file

- You can find MSFLXGRD.OCX (and other OCX files) on the internet. Save them to C:\windows\system32 (or syswow64) folder.
- You need regsvr32.exe and regedit.exe (or regedt32.exe). If you cannot find them in your computer, you can download them from internet.
- Start the command mode: C:>
- Go to C:\Windows\system32 (or syswow64).
- Run C:>Regsvr32 MSFLXGRD.OCX. If it shows “successfully installed”, you can continue.
- Run C:>Regedit vbctrls.reg or C:>regedt32 vbctrls.reg

如何註冊OCX 檔案

- 如果安裝時軟件顯示缺少某個 OCX 檔案 (例如：MSFLXGRD.OCX). 可以在網路上找到，將該檔案存於 C:\windows\system32 (或 syswow64) 檔案匣中。
- 安裝時必須使用 regsvr32.exe 與 regedit.exe (或 regedt32.exe). 若你的電腦上沒有這些檔案，可以上網搜尋。
- 啟動指令模式 `C:>_`
- 到 C:\Windows\system32 (or syswow64) 下。
- 執行 C:>Regsvr32 MSFLXGRD.OCX. 若顯示 “successfully installed”, 可以繼續下一步。
- 執行 C:>Regedit vbctrls.reg 或 C:>regedt32 vbctrls.reg
- 可以使用其他方法註冊 OCX 檔案。

Enter username. 輸入使用者姓名

Password

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Form4

Software License Agreement

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CONDITIONS.

You agree to cite following references:

(Note well: Honest citation is a protection for you to avoid accusation of unethical conduct).

If you use TWOSEX-MSChart program, you have to cite following reference:

1. Chi, H. 1988. Life-table analysis incorporating both sexes and variable development rate among individuals. *Environ. Entomol.* 17: 26-34.
2. Chi, H., and H. Liu. 1985. Two new methods for the study of insect population ecology. *Bull. Inst. Zool., Academia Sinica* 24: 225-240.
3. Chi, H. 2018. TWOSEX-MSChart: a computer program for the age-stage, two-sex life table analysis. <http://140.120.197.173/Ecology/>. (Please cite the Year in the TWOSEX program).

If you report the age-stage life expectancy (ex_j) or age-specific (ex) life expectancy you obtained from the TWOSEX program, you have to cite following reference:

1. Chi, H., and H. Y. Su. 2006. Age-stage, two-sex life tables of *Aphidius gifuensis* (Ashmead) (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) and its host *Myzus persicae* (Sulzer) (Homoptera: Aphididae) with mathematical proof of the relationship between female fecundity and the net reproductive rate. *Environmental Entomology* 35(1): 10-21.

If you report the group-reared life table based on the age-stage, two-sex life table, you have to cite following reference:

1. Chang, Cheng, Chun-Yen Huang, Shu-Mei Dai, Remzi Atlihan, and Hsin Chi. 2016. Genetically engineered ricin suppresses *Bactrocera dorsalis* (Diptera: Tephritidae) based on demographic analysis of group-reared life table. *Journal of Economic Entomology* 109(3): 987-992.

If you report the age-stage reproductive value (vx_j) or age-specific (vx) reproductive value you obtained from the TWOSEX program, you have to cite following references:

1. Tuan, Shu-Jen, Chung-Chieh Lee and Hsin Chi. 2014a. Population and damage projection of *Spodoptera litura* (F.) on peanuts (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) under different conditions using the age-stage, two-sex life table. *Pest Manag Sci.* 70: 805 -813.
2. Tuan, Shu-Jen, Chung-Chieh Lee and Hsin Chi. 2014b. Erratum: Population and damage projection of *Spodoptera litura* (F.) on peanuts (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) under different conditions using the age-stage, two-sex life table. *Pest Manag Sci.* 70: 1936.

If you report the 0.025 and 0.975 percentile life tables you obtained from the TWOSEX program, you have to cite following reference:

1. Huang, H. W., H. Chi, and C. L. Smith. 2018. Linking demography and consumption of *Henosepilachna vigintioctopunctata* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) fed on *Solanum photeinocarpum*: with a new method to project the uncertainty of population growth and consumption. *Journal of Economic Entomology.* 111(1): 1-9. doi: 10.1093/jee/tox330

If you collect your life table data using 2-, 4-, 5-day interval and analyze them using TWOSEX program, you have to cite following reference:

1. Zheng, Xiao-Min, Hsin Chi, Dong Chu. 2016. A simplified recording method for insect life table studies: a case study based on *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae). *Acta Entomologica Sinica* 59(6): 663-668.

If you use the 3-D life table, you have to cite following reference:

1. Hua, B. and H. Chi. 2011. The age-stage, two-sex life table with an offspring sex ratio dependent on female age. *Journal of Agriculture and Forestry* 60(4): 337-345.

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If you use TWOSEX, you must cite at least following references

- Chi, H., and H. Liu. 1985. Two new methods for the study of insect population ecology. Bull. Inst. Zool., Acad. Sin. 24: 225-240.
- Chi, H. 1988. Life-table analysis incorporating both sexes and variable development rates among individuals. Environ. Entomol. 17: 26-34.
- Chi, H. **2018**. TWOSEX-MSChart: a computer program for the age-stage, two-sex life table analysis. National Chung Hsing University, Taichung, Taiwan, (<http://140.120.197.173/Ecology/Download/TwoSEX-MSChart.zip>) (accessed 1 August **2018**). (Replace 2018 with the actual year you downloaded the program).

If you report life expectancy (e_{xj}), you must cite following references

Chi, H. and H. Y. Su. 2006. Age-stage, two-sex life tables of *Aphidius gifuensis* (Ashmead) (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) and its host *Myzus persicae* (Sulzer) (Homoptera: Aphididae) with mathematical proof of the relationship between female fecundity and the net reproductive rate. Environ. Entomol. 35: 10-21.

$$e_{xj} = \sum_{i=x}^{\infty} \sum_{y=j}^m s'_{iy}$$

If you report the reproductive value (v_{xj}), you must cite following references

- Fisher, R. A. 1930. The genetical theory of natural selection: a complete variorum edition. Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK.
- Huang, Y. B. and Hsin Chi. 2011. The age-stage, two-sex life table with an offspring sex ratio dependent on female age. *Journal of Agriculture and Forestry* 60: 337-345.
- Tuan, S. J., C. C. Lee, and H. Chi. 2014. Population and damage projection of *Spodoptera litura* (F.) on peanuts (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) under different conditions using the age-stage, two-sex life table. *Pest Management Science* 70: 805–813.
- Tuan, Shu-Jen, Chung-Chieh Lee and Hsin Chi. 2014b. Population and damage projection of *Spodoptera litura* (F.) on peanuts (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) under different conditions using the age-stage, two-sex life table. *Pest Manag Sci.* 70: 1936.

If you report the life table variability based on 0.025 and 0.975 percentile population, you must cite following references

Huang, H. W., H. Chi, and C. L. Smith. 2018. Linking demography and consumption of *Henosepilachna vigintioctopunctata* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) fed on *Solanum photeinocarpum*: with a new method to project the uncertainty of population growth and consumption. *Journal of Economic Entomology*. 111(1): 1–9.

Important review article

- Chi, H., M. S. You, R. Atlıhan, C. L. Smith, A. Kavousi, M. S. Özgökçe, A. Güncan, S. J. Tuan, J. W. Fu, Y. Y. Xu, F. Q. Zheng, B. H. Ye, D. Chu, Y. Yu, G. Gharekhani, P. Saska, T. Gotoh, M. I. Schneider, P. Bussaman, A. Gökçe, T. X. Liu. 2020. Age-Stage, Two-Sex Life Table: An Introduction to Theory, Data Analysis, and Application. *Entomologia Generalis* 40(2): 103-124. DOI: [10.1127/entomologia/2019/0936](https://doi.org/10.1127/entomologia/2019/0936).

New version and new paper

I update TWOSEX program frequently to improve the speed, add new functions, and add new output file. You are welcome to visit my web page to check the new version and new papers:

<http://140.120.197.173/ecology>

Teşekkür ederim!

سپاسگزارم

謝謝!

“À¼É¼İ¼

Děkuji

Danke!

¡Muchas gracias!

Thank you!

ご清聴ありがとうございます
います!